

1 **Appendix files of uncropped gel WB**

2

3 **Nitrate-Sialin Promotes Dentin Regeneration via**

4 **Mitochondrial Rewiring**

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Fig 1.

Fig 1H Control Aged Aged+nitrate

DSPP

HSP90

DMP1

Fig 1P Control H2O2 H2O2+nitrate

DSPP

HSP90

DMP1

Fig 1X Control Eto Eto+nitrate

DSPP

HSP90

DMP1

HSP90

Fig 2N Control Nitrate shSLC17A5 shSLC17A5+nitrate

Fig 3G Control Nitrate shSLC17A5 shSLC17A5+nitrate

Fig 4A Control Nitrate Rotenons Rotenone+nitrate

DSPP

HSP90

DMP1

GAPDH

Sialin

GAPDH

ACO2

PDH E1 GAPDH

IDH2

GAPDH

GAPDH p21

Appendix Fig 3

Appendix Fig 3F H₂O₂ H₂O₂ + NaNO₃ H₂O₂ + KNO₃ H₂O₂ + NaCl H₂O₂ + KCl

p16

p21

HSP90

Appendix Fig 3P Young Aged Aged+nitrate

p16

HSP90

